

Industry 4.0 projects' background and our experiences at the wood industrial manufactories

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the applied IT solutions during the operation of factories is to support the manufacturing workflow and the strategic decision making of company managers. We reviewed the industrial techniques in nowadays and the newest trends (“Industrial Internet”, “Industry 4.0”) which are based on the idea of “Internet of things”. In our research, we have analyzed the economical background, the multinational and local platforms of Industry 4.0 and the new IT techniques, which support Industry 4.0. In the second part of our paper, we have investigated two case studies, which are related to the wood industrial companies. We have summarized the company’s problems, environments, and given possible solutions for their problems.

Introduction

Substantial technological advances appeared in the industrial sector in the last years. Developments are based on the “Internet of things” (IoT) idea, called as “Industry 4.0” in Europe. The name is referring to the phenomena that many experts think this is the 4th industrial revolution. The goal of these projects is to create live connections among all industrial machines, tools and the decentralized units. Some techniques and tools, e.g., sensors, big data, cloud computing, real-time capability, virtualization and artificial intelligence, support the IT developments also [1]. The decision making in the industry will be automated and quick because of the new methods and tools. The following section introduces these techniques and their possibilities in the industrial sector.

After this, we are focusing on the wood industrial sector. We have chosen two wood industrial companies. Their problems will be demonstrated in the following section. Their main goal is to reduce their costs and waste. Therefore, they must (1) integrate their separated systems, (2) collect their data from different sources, (3) analyse their data (4) connect their machines to each other, (5) control their processes etc. We are collaborating with several companies in the wood industrial sector helping them to reach the high level of integration. The last section concludes the paper.

Integrated systems and “Industrial Internet”

The meaning of the Industry 4.0 is the following: extended data collector, data processing, visualization and control system, that is integrated with Internet technologies in an industrial environment. This system has a close connection with the physical integrated environment, and gives information and optimizes about the operation of the plant. The operation of the system will function more effective because of the following reasons:

- the system can't function better just because of the connection and the availability of the data,
- that's why it is needed such an important system part, that can make more effective the operation of the whole system with the using of the data, and it needs less human intervention.

The configured system with the objectives of the Industry 4.0 is a distributed and extensive IT system and its related physical system, in that the IT part is intervening in the operation of the physical part by the

collected information (CPS¹). In the previous and existing (outdated) industrial systems, the earlier mentioned intervention of the workers doesn't dare to commit fully to the machine, that's why generally a human decision terminates the production process. Further goals, that the optimization of the operation of the system: in case of failures, it can work effective thereby it pays attention to the cost effectiveness and the prevention of the unexpected events.

Every IoT solution collects data, that leads to the analysing of the data. The analytics results interventions or actions, which lead to increase outcomes or decrease cost or both of them.

As we mentioned, the goal of the companies is to reach the higher level of integration. There are two parts of integration: horizontal and vertical [2]. The *horizontal integration* means that the company and its partners (suppliers, customers etc.) are in one integrated system. The products can be tracked and traced from the suppliers to the costumers. The *vertical integration* means that every machine in the factory are connected to the decentralized centres [3]. These machines' data are the bases of the managers' analyses. These computes may be run in the cloud, because this computing is one of the Industry 4.0's techniques. The analyzation of big data collection becomes simpler this way. In Fig. 1, we can see the levels and types of integration from the viewpoint of a traditional business model. The supply chains contain a set of firms, that is working together to deliver value by transforming raw material into a finished product [4].

Figure 1. The supply chain (left side) and the levels of integration

New IT techniques at the industrial field

In this subsection, we will introduce new IT techniques, which support the 4th industrial revolution.

Big Data

Everything can be measured by sensors in the factory, so the sensors collect data about the production, the environment of the firm etc. Lots of data are generated every second while the company is operating. The productivity and the effectivity are continuously increasing at the factory. So, we have large volume

¹ Cyber-Physical System

of data, which is called “big data” in a new IT terminology. (*Volume* identifies the size of data.) Several terms connect to the “Big Data” definition [5].

“*Big data is high-volume, high-velocity and high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making.*” (“Gartner IT Glossary, n. d.”)

“*Big data is a term that describes large volumes of high velocity, complex and variable data that require advanced techniques and technologies to enable the capture, storage, distribution, management, and analysis of the information.*” (Tech America Foundation’s Federal Big Data Commission, 2012)

“*Big Data combines information from diverse sources in new ways to create knowledge, make better predictions.*” [4]

The large volume of data is useless without analytics. The traditional statistical methods are not sufficient for analysing these data, we have to use data mining and other techniques [6]. To use the big data correctly, we need to examine the whole process which supports the decision making.

Figure 2. Big data processes, which support the decision making [7]

First, the *data management* involves processes and supporting technologies to acquire and store data and to prepare and retrieve it for analysis. Second, *analytics* refers to techniques used to analyse and acquire intelligence from big data. We can see, the big data without analytics is useless. Thus, we must apply analytical methods for analysing our data in the factory. These calculating may run in our private cloud.

There are a lot of ways to analyse the data sets and to get information, e.g., standard reports, ad hoc reports, OLAP², alerts about alarms and malfunctions, statistical analysis, key performance indicators, forecasting, predictive modelling, optimization. We are concentrating to the predictive analytics methods.

The *predictive analytics* include several techniques, which predict the future outcomes based on the historical and current data. These analytics can be applied in the industrial field perfectly. These analytics are based on the statistical methods, furthermore, it has several “extensions” for handling special big data sets. The predictive analytics have to manage (1) the heterogenous data from different sources, (2) the amount of noise, (3) the random correlation in the data sets [8].

Other IT techniques

We briefly review a few other methods and standards below, that also support the availability and development of the industrial internet projects.

² On-Line Analytical Processing

- *Cloud computing*: a set of virtualized computers (lots of virtual machines), that is able to analyse the big data sets more efficient.
- *Interoperability*: a co-operation between the trimmer units, the employees, the users and the internet of things [9].
- *Virtualization*: we can create a virtual firm with helping of sensors. In these virtual plants, there can be the same industrial processes as in the real production. It follows, that the industrial processes can be designed at higher abstraction level [10].
- *Decentralization*: there isn't one centre in the firm. There are several central units, which work in parallel way. One centre is able to substitute the other ones [11].
- *Real time capability*: the analysis and the evaluation of the data are at the same time.
- *Service orientation*: the sets of services can be extendible at the company.
- *Modularity*: every component can be exchangeable easily.

Hungarian industry from the viewpoint of Industry 4.0

The Industry 4.0 project is at the beginning in the Hungarian manufacturing sector. However, the digitalization of the Hungarian industry is on a higher level. There are different financial sources from European Union and the Hungarian government to support this digitalization process. To have a better understanding of the Hungarian industry from the viewpoint of Industry 4.0, we have analysed the report of Roland Berger, e.g., European countries' Industry 4.0 Readiness Index (this can be seen in Fig. 3).

Figure 3. RB's Industry 4.0 Readiness Index (Source: https://www.rolandberger.com/publications/publication_pdf/roland_berger_tab_industry_4_0_20140403.pdf)

The reason of using the Internet of Things technology in the industrial field:

- now: the companies can reduce the cost of operation, and prevent the failure or stoppage of the production line

- in the future, the companies gain extra profit via service-oriented production system and the managers' needs will be satisfied for easier decision making.

The IT support of Industry 4.0 in EU and Hungary

One of the most innovative companies, the General Electric (GE) has become a software and analytical company from an industrial company in the last years. GE is the leader of the Industry 4.0 projects in EU. GE identifies the main problem in the industrial environment: *"80% of an analytics project typically involves gathering and then preparing the data for analysis."*³ Therefore, they have developed their IT framework (GE Historian powered by Predix), solutions and platform (Predix platform), which support common storage, management, integration and access of heterogenous data. These data are stored in the GE's "Industrial Data Lake".

The GE's solutions motivate and inspire the Hungarian experts and researchers to develop their own solution. It is called SensorHub. Now, they are searching project-partners for testing their SensorHub platform. The developers of SensorHub are cooperating with the software and hardware specialists, who implement solutions for exploring and monitoring network, collecting data, evaluating time series, alarming operators etc. We would like to establish a solution, which is capable to solve similar tasks, which we mentioned just now.

There are different production systems and techniques. Every company is unique in the industrial field and they have unique production systems. But they have similar problems in their production progress. We summarize these problems and give solutions to solve them.

In general, Hungarian wood industrial companies had to implement several unique developments before they propose a new plan for dealing with Industry 4.0's standards.

Wood industrial case studies

In these sections, we will summarize two case studies, which are connecting to the IoT in the wood industrial field.

Case study 1: the production of garden's wooden-houses

We have investigated the company's environment, which includes its processes, software, hardware. Our experiences will be demonstrated in this subsection. First, we describe the problems of the company, then, we recommend several solutions for them.

IT problems at the company

We describe their main problems, and the problems' environment.

In our first case study, three different problems are mapped:

1. The company gets too many complaints from its customers because of the missing components of the wooden-house. The observation of these missing components is a complex problem. The measurement of the wooden-house package is not a good solution, because the weight differences of the packages can be 10-20 kg because of moisture content of the wooden-components.
2. In the plant, the wooden-materials are shaved by a plane machine. After that, a human worker investigates the timber board color, which may be dark, light or ok. Furthermore, the shaved timbers – ordered by the company – are not analyzed by anybody.

³ Source: A Software Platform for Operational Technology Innovation, International Data Corporation (IDC), 2014

3. The company has several different systems, which controls different processes. These systems are not integrated to each other. For example: three employees would like to go holiday next week, it may cause problems at the production progress or the warehouse's operation.

By solving these problems, they will be able to collect and analyze their data for getting information about their processes.

Solution types at the company

In our first case study, we recommend three solutions for the mentioned problems one by one:

1. There are two possible ways to solve the first problem:
 - a. The managers should make the RFID installation for identifying all components, which are connected to the full package of the wooden-houses. We have investigated the costs and risks of the established RFID system.
 - i. The system environment contains passive and active RFID tags, reader, data collector, and the controlling middleware machine.
 - ii. We must handle the following risks: electromagnetic interference (EMI), signal-loss, RFID antenna's wrong initialization etc.
 - b. The company's recommendation, that we should build a camera-based computer vision system, we rejected at the beginning. The main reason of the rejection is the irregular packing techniques of the workers.
2. The company should launch a software and hardware development for determining timbers' color value. We installed and customized such a system at another company earlier (See [12] reference).
3. The company must initiate an ERP⁴ system (e.g., SAP or Microsoft Dynamics AX / NAV) [13][14]. This one can handle problems, that's why integrated solutions are needed.

In 2017, the company's director has decided to initiate the SAP ERP system first, after that, the Industry 4.0 solutions have been able to implemented at the company [15].

Case study 2: Energy management standard at a wood industrial company

In this section, we demonstrate a development process and its problems. The furniture company's experts know their heterogeneous systems. The main goal at the company is to initiate the ISO 50001 Energy management standard.

During the project, we concentrate the energy usage/consumption of the machines. We generate targeted reports with the help of the collected data to the managers of the company. We consider during the configuration of the system the goals of the Industry 4.0 too, namely for the future decision making. The goals will be the following:

- To correspond to the standards of the ISO 50001 Energy Management System.
- The correct meaning of the data will be useful to the future energy usage planning.
- With the help of the configured system, we can answer the following questions for the past events:
 - What happened when?
 - e.g., excessive energy consumption.
 - How often and where happened? How often happened where?
 - e.g., stoppage.
 - Where exactly is the problem?
 - e.g., the specific settings of the machine operator.

⁴ Enterprise Resource Planning

- When should I react and how?
 - e.g., the typing of the alert levels into the system.
- Why is this happening?
 - e.g., in the industrial machines, what kinds of products are produced.
- Our goals, with the help of the configured system we can answer the following questions for the future events:
 - What if these trends continue?
 - e.g., with the monitoring of the trends will be predictable the critic periods, out-ages, failures of the machines.
 - How much is needed?
 - e.g., we can save on the energy costs, if we know better the operational needs of the plants.
 - What will happen next?
 - How do we do things better?
 - e.g., if we start to modify the setting of the producing machines while the production progress.
 - What is the best decision for a complex problem?
 - e.g., if we want take into a new machine in the production system, then we can plan better with the costs.

In the Figure 4. The Analytics Continuum (Source: Extend Your Portfolio of Analytics Capabilities, Gartner, 2013), a part of these questions and the variety of human interfering is illustrated

Figure 4. The Analytics Continuum (Source: Extend Your Portfolio of Analytics Capabilities, Gartner, 2013)

In our second case study, the main problem is the diversity of the systems. The company has several systems (ERP⁵, DBMS⁶ etc.) and a lot of disconnected sensors.

ISO 50001 Energy management standard requirements

The ISO 50001 defines the requirements, that are necessary for the companies to establish their energy management systems. The initiation of ISO 50001 takes advantages to the small and large organizations, manufacturing companies and service providers in the whole world. The standard provides frameworks to the energy management of factories.

The availability of the energy is very important to every organizations, and it is the main cost factor inde-

⁵ Enterprise Resource Planning

⁶ Database Management System

pendently the company's activity. Beside the economic costs, there are other costs in related to the consumption of electricity (e.g., environmental costs). The optimizing of the usage of the energy resources increases the energy efficiency, and decreases the energy costs. The base of the ISO 50001 is a world-wide well-known and implemented system model, that facilitates the application of the energy management system.

The main goals, that are feasible with the help of ISO 50001, are the followings:

- It supports the organizations in a better usage of the existing energy consumption devices.
- It helps to the companies to evaluate the new energy-efficient technologies.
- It ensures the management commitment, that the energy management is valuable for the company.
- It demonstrates the environmental commitment of the companies towards the costumers.
- It supports the implementation of the projects, that contain the decreasing of the harmful environmental effects of the company.
- It increases the competitiveness of the company at the market.

The system can be integrated in existing management systems, because the structure and the requirements of the ISO 50001 standard are very similar to the ISO 14001 standard. Thanks to this similarity the energy management system can be installed easily.

Hardware and software environment at company's system

A possible solution for the problems is an integrated building supervision system can control the production machines' current supply. We have surveyed the company's hardware and software environment, for which we have to adapt.

There are two plants at the company's park. In the plants, the machines do their different manufacturing jobs. These machines are connecting to three computer servers, which make surveys and monitoring functions principally. We have investigated the functions and interfaces of the servers:

1. "MOVEX operator" server:
 - a. This is a self-developed hardware and software tool, which is counting the workpieces, which go through the production machines.
 - b. Given the databases' structures, the MOVEX operator servers are different in the plants.
 - i. Therefore, we must implement different data collecting solutions for two plants.
2. MOVEX ERP system:
 - a. The corporate processes' data structures in the ERP are the same in the plants.
 - b. These data are synchronizing continually to the center server of the multinational company.
3. There is working a building supervisory system at the company, however, this system can partially handle the complex problem of the consumption of electricity.
 - a. There is a need for additional calculation. The supervisory system gives us the summation data, from which we can get back the set of raw data. (Technically, we use an SQL server.)
 - i. With using of different techniques, we can compute the approximate energy usage per machine: subtracting the overhead, getting the subareas' cumulative energy consumption.
 - b. The company's experts are able to monitor or modify the production machines' management.
 - c. The system's data storage is working like a black box; however, we can make incremental saves, which are exported to the MySQL databases (or tables).

- d. Our self-developed solution's data are also stored in a MySQL database.

The production machines' energy consumption can be constant, but they produce circa 1500 items with different numbers. Furthermore, when the energy limit exceeded at the company, it has to pay penalty for the power provider company. So, we have several requirements by our solutions' implementation.

The integration is important at the company, because the data owners have their own data, but the connections between every data sources are not solved. The given problem is the synchronization of the clock of machines, however, we have possible solutions for that: IEEE 1588-2008 (v2) Standard for a Precision Clock Synchronization Protocol for Networked Measurement and Control Systems, Time-Sensitive Networking, P802.1Qcc – Stream Reservation Protocol, P802.1Qbv – Enhancements for Scheduled Traffic, P802.1AS-Revision – Timing and Synchronization, P802.1Qbu – Frame Preemption etc.

Conclusion

We have introduced the Industry 4.0 project standards, requirements, the levels of integration, and its supporting techniques for example: the big data, cloud computing etc. Then, we have analyzed the European and the Hungarian situations from the viewpoint of Industry 4.0. We have briefly summarized the applied platforms and frameworks. In the second part of our paper, we have got on to a subject of the wood industrial case studies. We have defined two companies' problems and environment and our suggestions. In the second case study, we have started to implement an integrated energy management system, which will be developed following the standards and requirements of Industry 4.0.

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